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EPIDEMIOLOGY OF HIV INFECTION IN VARIOUS SOCIAL GROUPS IN FERGANA REGION

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Abstract: HIV (human immunodeficiency virus) is a chronic infectious disease that persists in the human body throughout life. It destroys the immune system, the system that protects the body from external dangerous influences. Its peculiarity is that in the initial period after the virus enters the body, no unpleasant symptoms are felt, the immune system suppresses the aggression of viruses. In our country, the Republican HIV/AIDS Center, the HIV/AIDS Center of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the HIV/AIDS Centers of Tashkent city and regions carry out all preventive, epidemiological, laboratory testing, and treatment activities related to this area of activity in their territories.

This article provides information on the study of the epidemiological characteristics of HIV infection in various social groups in the Fergana region, as well as preventive measures.

Keywords: HIV infection, incidence, prevalence, indicator.

Relevance of the topic: HIV infection has become one of the most pressing problems facing the World Health Organization today. Today, there are about 41 million patients suffering from HIV infection in the world. Their number is increasing by an average of 1.5 million per year. Worse, the disease claims the lives of more than 600,000 people every year. By the end of 2023, the number of people infected with HIV and those who have been infected with the disease on our planet will be 39.9 million, and the number of newly infected will be 1.3 [1–1.7] million. This data is an increase of 4.2 [3.0–5.7] million compared to 2014. [1,2,3,12].

Currently, the incidence of HIV infection is more common in the population of our Republic aged 25 to 45. Currently, 53.3% of men and 46.7% of women are infected with this disease, and as of January 1, 2024, the number of people living with HIV infection was 49.1 thousand [5,7,8,10].

According to the results of a retrospective analysis of HIV infection in the Fergana region in 2007-2023; since 2007, a 1.84-fold increase in the disease has been detected, and the number of people infected with HIV has increased significantly over 16 years. In 2007, this indicator was 214 people, and by 2023 it reached 394 people. The period of the greatest decrease in the disease is considered to be the transition period from 2018 to 2019. During this period, the number of infected people decreased from 355 to 242, a decrease of 113 people [4,6,9,15].

According to the demographic analysis of people living with HIV in Fergana region as of January 1, 2024, the number of men was 2,296, indicating that this is the group with the highest prevalence of HIV infection. Among women, 1,875 people living with HIV were registered, and among children under 18 years of age, 430 people living with HIV were registered. Also, 1,694 people died from HIV-related diseases, which confirms the need to improve treatment and prevention measures [11,14,13,16].

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The purpose of the study: To study the epidemiological characteristics of HIV infection in various social groups in the Fergana region and to improve its prevention.

Research material and methods: In order to study the characteristics of the epidemiological process of HIV infection in the Fergana region, official data on HIV infection from the Fergana Regional Center for HIV/AIDS Control for 2007-2023 were studied and retrospectively analyzed. As well as the results of HIV tests in diagnostic laboratories. The study used retrospective and operational epidemiological analysis methods.

Research results: Currently, an uneven distribution of HIV infection among different social groups has been identified in Fergana region.

If we look at social groups in Fergana region, more cases of infection were observed among labor migrants. Migration processes have their impact on the spread of HIV infection among the population. The disease is significant in that it is registered in large numbers among different age groups, especially among young people. During 2010–2023, the detection of HIV infection among labor migrants in the region shows significant changes. While only 7 cases of HIV infection were registered among labor migrants in 2010, the number of detected cases has increased sharply since 2015. In particular, in 2015, 127 people were infected with HIV among migrant workers, and in 2018 this figure increased to 132, indicating an increase in the spread of HIV infection during this period. In 2022, the number of detected cases reached 114, which was one of the highest figures. In 2023, a slight decrease was observed, with 108 cases recorded. In recent years, the acceleration of migration processes has led to an increase in the number of people leaving for foreign countries in order to earn money. Their poor living conditions, lack of access to medical services, and other factors also contribute to the increase in the incidence of the disease among migrants.

According to the results of laboratory testing of medical workers for HIV infection in the region in 2022-2023: In 2022, a total of 40,790 medical workers were tested in the region, of whom 5 were diagnosed with HIV infection. In 2023, the number of those tested reached 44,374, and HIV infection was detected in 6 cases. The analysis shows that the expansion of diagnostic coverage and the strengthening of preventive measures throughout the region have increased the possibility of early detection of HIV infection. This is important in controlling the epidemic situation.

In Fergana region, 12 cases of HIV infection among pregnant women were recorded in 2017, while in 2018-2019 this figure reached 16, reaching its highest point. In 2020, detections decreased again to 12, but in 2021 there was an increase with 14 cases. In 2022, the lowest figure was 11, and in 2023 this number reached 13. Further strengthening of preventive and diagnostic measures will help to detect and reduce this infection early.

As a result of the measures taken to ensure the implementation of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures to combat the spread of the disease caused by the human immunodeficiency virus and prevent hospital-acquired infections” No. PQ-3800 dated June 22, 2020, the epidemic situation with HIV infection in the Republic has stabilized in recent years.

Measures to prevent mother-to-child transmission of HIV infection in the Republic are organized on the basis of the protocols of the World Health Organization. In accordance with them, each woman is monitored by a local medical institution until the 12th week of pregnancy and is medically tested for HIV infection. A pregnant woman who is diagnosed with HIV infection is provided with special preventive drugs against the virus from the period specified in the protocol until delivery.

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Treatment and prevention institutions should be fully and timely provided with reusable and single-use medical devices, medical supplies, and consumables.

Conclusion:

1. If we consider the Fergana region by social groups, the disease is significant in that it is registered in large numbers among different age groups, especially among young people. The detection of HIV infection among labor migrants in the region during 2010-2023 shows significant changes. While in 2010 only 7 cases were registered among labor migrants, the number of detected cases has increased sharply since 2015. In particular, in 2015, 127 people were infected with HIV among labor migrants. In 2022, the number of detected cases reached 114, which was one of the highest indicators. In 2023, a slight decrease was observed, with 108 cases registered. Due to the acceleration of migration processes in recent years, the number of people leaving for foreign countries to earn money is increasing. Their precarious living conditions, lack of access to medical services, and other factors also contribute to the increased incidence of disease among migrants.

2. According to the results of laboratory testing of medical workers for HIV infection in 2022-2023: a total of 40,790 medical workers underwent laboratory testing, of which 5 were diagnosed with HIV infection. In 2023, the number of those tested reached 44,374, and HIV was detected in 6 cases. As a result of the expansion of the diagnostic coverage of tests and the strengthening of preventive measures throughout the region, the possibility of early detection of HIV infection was created.

3. In the region, 12 cases of HIV infection among pregnant women were recorded in 2017, while in 2018-2019 this figure reached 16, reaching its highest point. In 2020, the number of detections decreased again to 12, but in 2021 there was an increase with 14 cases. In 2022, the lowest figure was 11, and in 2023 this number reached 13. As a result, further strengthening of preventive and diagnostic measures helped to detect and reduce the infection.

In conclusion, it can be said that it is necessary to take measures to prevent the disease. In this regard, we need to promote a healthy lifestyle among all segments of the population, especially among young people, avoid promiscuous and unprotected sex, ensure that medical equipment is disinfected when receiving medical treatment, pay attention to the hygienic cleanliness of the equipment used in the service when using household services (hairdressing and shaving, manicure, pedicure, tattooing), take measures to prevent the spread of HIV infection, and improve the spiritual well being of the younger generation.

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